

Alliance Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 18th April 2024

Introduction

On 18th of April 2023, the UK Health Data Research Alliance (the Alliance) convened its second Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum, chaired by Professor Matthew Sydes and Associate Professor Marion Mafham. The forum, attended by over 35 stakeholders from diverse sectors including clinical trialists, regulatory bodies, data custodians, funding organisations, clinicians, and academic researchers. It aimed to address challenges in utilising healthcare system data for clinical trials and prioritise actions to unlock potential benefits. Presentations covered topics such as consent wording for trial participants to allow data linkage, the NHS DigiTrials initiative, data linkage in national research in Wales, and managing access to health data for trials in Scotland. The presentations were followed by breakout sessions to facilitate conversations around the higher priority challenges in data access, and how to solve them.

The session aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Explore the challenges faced by data custodians in providing access to data for clinical trials and consented cohorts, with a focus on understanding the specific barriers and constraints they encounter.
2. Identify and discuss the potential costs and impacts associated with addressing the challenges highlighted by data custodians, researchers and other stakeholders involved in clinical trials and cohort studies.
3. Facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing among data custodians, researchers, and other stakeholders to identify priority actions to overcome the barriers to accessing data for clinical trials and consented cohorts.

All presentations are available on the [UK Health Data Research Alliance website](#).

Kate Roberts | CrossWord: Consent to access and use routine health data – appropriate wording for participant-facing materials of randomised clinical trials

The presentations began with Kate Roberts (PhD student at UCL's MRC CTU), highlighting the challenges surrounding consent for accessing routine health data in randomised clinical trials, such as the lack of clear wording in participant materials, inconsistent governance requirements across data providers, and varying interpretations of patient consent. The "CrossWord" project aims to address these challenges by effectively future-proofing participant-facing materials, improving transparency, and fostering trust by enabling consent to data access. The project's approach includes 6 phases:

1. Scoping visits to UK Clinical Trials Units (CTUs)
2. Initial review of wording in participant-facing materials

3. Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) focus groups to obtain views on current and historical consent materials
4. Interviews or focus groups with data providers and trialists who have successfully accessed healthcare systems data (HSD)
5. Co-developing consent guidance in consultation with PPIE groups
6. Refining guidance through consultation with the Health Research Authority (HRA) and UK data custodians

The slides from this presentation can be found [here](#).

Heather Pinches | NHS DigiTrials

Heather Pinches (Head of NHS DigiTrials and Research Products, NHS England) presented work being delivered by the Data and Analytics Directorate. The presentation focused on the NHS DigiTrials service portfolio, which encompasses several key data services to support clinical trials including: feasibility, recruitment, communication with patients, and outcomes. These are at different stages of development, so Recruitment is in the pilot stage, but the Outcomes service is live. The Feasibility service is being developed further to provide information by hospital trusts.

Regarding challenges to accessing HSD for clinical trials and cohort studies, NHS DigiTrials have been focussing on ensuring data usability. A linkage methodology pipeline has been developed to bring data assets together. These become very large, very quickly and sustainability is a challenge. In the future, they are seeking feedback on how to priorities which products they develop for automation and how to streamline governance. Further information regarding DigiTrials clinical trials support is available on [their website](#).

The slides from this session can be found [here](#).

Jon Smart | SAIL Databank – Data linkage supporting national research – Clinical trials and cohort studies

Jon Smart (Head of Programmes and Chief Operating Officer, SAIL Databank), followed on with a presentation on SAIL Databank and its applicability to clinical trials.

With over 32 billion records covering more than 5 million individuals, SAIL offers comprehensive data resources, including 80% coverage of GP practices in Wales and full access to NHS secondary care data, allied health services, provisioning, and screening. SAIL actively supports clinical trials, managing both consented and anonymised cohorts and facilitating data linkage for research purposes.

The presentation included particular focus on adherence to legal frameworks governing data processing and management. Access to data can be through their TRE, but data must remain there. Access outside of the TRE is subject to strict legal basis and governance review. Notably, they stress the importance of obtaining fully informed consent from trial participants for data extraction a

process rigorously scrutinised by the legal team. Only with explicit consent and legal approval can data be released and utilised.

The Information Governance Review Panel oversees these processes, comprising diverse members from various sectors to ensure ethical data use and alignment with public benefit objectives. Challenges, such as discovery processes and leveraging data for identifying suitable patients or populations in ongoing consented trials, highlight the SAIL's commitment to advancing research while upholding stringent data protection standards.

The slides from this presentation can be found [here](#).

James Watson | Managing access to health data for clinical trials

James Watson (Research Coordinator, Public Health Scotland - eDRIS), presented a comprehensive overview of the organisation's role in supporting research and clinical trials in Scotland, along with the challenges encountered and future plans.

eDRIS plays a pivotal role in Scotland's research ecosystem by collaborating with regional trusted research environments and organisations such as Research Data Scotland (RDS) and HDRUK, aiming to improve data access across the country. While not directly involved in initiatives such as the SHARE Register, it actively supports clinical trial research and engages in information governance processes, collaborating closely with NHS boards for data access.

Key support services offered by eDRIS include feasibility analysis, patient cohort identification, and participation in the HDRUK Cohort Discovery tool. Despite facing challenges primarily related to information governance and technical issues, eDRIS has successfully provided national data for numerous clinical trials and research studies. Noteworthy successes include facilitating service improvements, such as linking CHI numbers to residential addresses and supporting studies like the SCOT-HEART study. Issues faced include ensuring accurate data linkage, and providing data as close to "live data" as possible.

The slides from this presentation can be found [here](#).

Breakout sessions and key themes:

Attendees were split into breakout sessions to discuss the below question and the key themes were captured.

Which is the highest priority challenge and how to solve it? Reach a decision by discussing:

- What are the biggest challenges to accessing high-quality data for clinical trials (and other prospectively consented cohorts)?
- How does planned use of the data impact on this?
- Who is best placed to tackle these challenges?
- How should we prioritise these challenges, in terms of cost and impact?

Further details regarding the breakout sessions and the discussions had can be found in this [supplementary document](#).

Complex Legal Frameworks and Standardising Consent Procedures

Participants across the breakout rooms highlighted the challenges posed by complex legal frameworks, including GDPR and common law, which can lead to delays and uncertainty in data access processes. Fragmented information governance and varied regulations across regions exacerbate these issues. The administrative burden of navigating permissions, obtaining, and maintaining approvals, and adapting to changing requirements during the data application process was a significant concern.

There was a consensus on the need to standardise consent procedures to streamline the approval process while ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements. Ensuring transparency to the public regarding data usage and integrating clear guidelines for onward data sharing, especially with countries lacking adequacy agreements, were also deemed crucial. Participants noted the importance of balancing understandable consent materials with enabling broad data access and the necessity of harmonising processes across the UK to mitigate the differential processes affecting population inclusion in studies. This theme highlights the importance of clarity and consistency in navigating legal complexities to facilitate efficient data access for clinical trials and other research endeavours.

Building Capacity and Expertise within Trial Teams

Another key theme was the necessity of building capacity and expertise within trial teams to effectively navigate governance issues associated with data access. Participants emphasised the need for central support services or navigator roles to assist researchers in producing approval-ready applications. Expertise within existing teams for accessing and managing data exports, and clarifications on data transfer security and access permissions, especially in sponsored drug trials, were highlighted as critical needs.

Additionally, capturing institutional knowledge from previous projects was identified as a valuable strategy to inform decision-making and reduce redundancy. Addressing the challenges in recruiting staff with the required technical skills, especially in academia compared to industry salaries, and providing training and support for clinical trials units were seen as essential steps. Infrastructure alignment and harmonisation across information governance, technology, capacity, and training were also discussed. This theme addresses the importance of investing in resources and training to empower trialists, streamline the data access process, and ensure that the necessary expertise is available to tackle governance complexities due to differing legal approaches across the four nations.

Patient Involvement in and Streamlining Decision-Making Processes

Participants highlighted the crucial role of patients and the public in shaping data access policies, emphasising the importance of respecting patients' wishes and involving them in decision-making

processes. There was a call to simplify the decision-making process by reducing the number of groups involved in approving data access requests and promoting consistency in decision-making across different review bodies. Ensuring accurate matching processes for returning the right participants and maintaining transparency about data usage were also highlighted.

Participants discussed the timeliness of data acquisition and the need for clear processes and timelines for obtaining data from providers. Identifying access points for data and defining phenotypes and outcome measures were considered vital to improve efficiency. Addressing recruitment challenges, ensuring equality and inclusivity of trial participants, and involving Patients, Public, Involvement, and Engagement (PPIE) to support expanded data access were also emphasised. There is a clear need for transparent and patient-centred approaches to data access for clinical trials, ensuring that research efforts align with the needs of study participants and simplifying the application process to reduce delays and enhance the overall efficiency of data access.

Next steps:

Future meetings have been scheduled as below.

- Wednesday 11th September 2024 (14:00 – 15:30)

An agenda and Eventbrite registration link for the next meeting will be shared with all participants shortly. If you have suggestions for discussion topics, please share your ideas with us.

Appendix

Contributing Organisations
Cystic Fibrosis Trust
Cardiff University
Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD)
Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust
Health & Social Care Delivery Research programme
Health and Social Care Northern Ireland
Health Data Research UK
King's College London
Leeds Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust
Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)
NHS Data for Research and Development Programme (NHSE)
NHS DigiTrials (NHSE)
Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences
Optimum Patient Care
Our Future Health
Public Health Scotland
Swansea University
The Royal Marsden
The Scottish Government, Chief Scientist's Office
Understanding Patient Data
University College London
University of Dundee
University of Oxford
University of Southampton